

Cultural monuments in the Ferghana Valley

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Abstract: This article is about cultural monuments in the Fergana Valley. People have been living in the Fergana Valley since ancient times. The cultural monuments here cover the period from the Stone Age to the present day. the monuments belonging to the periods are found and studied.

Key words: Ferghana Valley, periods, Simtepa, Selungur Cave, Chust culture, archaeological research, Kuva, Chust, stone weapons.

Enter

Fergana region is one of the centers of ancient culture of Uzbekistan. Stone age settlements and pictures on rocks found in the region indicate that people have been living in the valley since the earliest times. Excavation of the Big Fergana canal in the study of archaeological monuments in Fergana region. became important. During the excavation of the canal, relics of the Bronze Age and slave and zamindari societies were found and examined. It was found that there was a Bronze Age settlement in the village of Akbarabad between Kuva and Tashloq districts, and an Oktom cemetery on the left bank of Margilansay. Monuments such as Tachyontepa and Simtepa in the city of Fergana have been found and studied in Kuva district of Fergana region. In particular, the findings of the 5th century BC and the beginning of the middle century in the city of Kuva have been well investigated. There, at the end of the Bronze Age, the development of production forces and economy led to a change in the social structure of the farming tribes, resulting in the end of the primitive order and social stratification.

Discussion

The results of archeological investigations indicate that people lived in Fergana region since ancient times, engaged in hunting, farming and cattle breeding, and culture began to develop in the later stages of human society. If we give a separate definition to each settlement, the oldest of them is the Selung'ur cave.

Seleng'ur Cave is an ancient settlement in Sokh District, Fergana Valley. The cave is located approximately 100 km southwest of the city of Fergana, on the western

edge of Haydarkon. This huge cave is 120 m deep, 34 m wide and 25 m high. Archaeological excavations have been carried out since 1980. Five cultural layers with a thickness of 20-40 cm were found in the cave. They are separated by clean layers without any archaeological remains. This indicates that primitive people lived in this cave 5 times and occasionally left their homes for a long time. A rich collection of stone weapons, remains of animal bones, and human remains of the archanthropic type were found here. When determining the age of Seleng'ur, scientists also gave a general conclusion that they lived 800,000 years ago[1.21].

Chust culture is an ancient farming culture in the Fergana Valley. The inhabitants who created this culture were at first engaged in animal husbandry, and later moved to a sedentary lifestyle. Their first village was found in 1951 by M.E. Voronets near the spring called Buvanamozor near the city of Chust. Archaeologists gave this monument the name of the Chust culture because the settlement near the monument was the city of Chust[1.87].

In Chust, after M.E. Voronets, V.I. Sprishevskii, B. Matboboev, Yu.A. Zadneprovsky conducted research. Excavations were carried out in monuments such as Dalvarzintepa, Karakurgan, Torakurgan, Tergovchi. In them, the cultural layer has been preserved up to 1.5-3 meters, which indicates that the inhabitants of the Chust culture lived a sedentary life later. shows that the content has been found. The inhabitants of this culture are the indigenous inhabitants of Central Asia, and they belong to the European type in terms of physical structure and anthropological type.

Summary

Many settlements of people have been found in the Fergana Valley. In the course of their study, the first tools and bones of primitive people were found in these places. New settlements are also being discovered and recorded. Most of the results of the archaeological expeditions, which were of great importance in the study of the archeology of the Ferghana Valley, have not been published, which may cause some problems in the study of the history of the valley. But among the researches published in different periods, the information about the purpose, composition, achievements of these expeditions can fill some empty links in the archeology and history of the Ferghana Valley. Of course, it is important to give a historiographical conclusion at this point. The comparative analysis of the achievements and shortcomings of the expeditions has a key role in the development of not only the history of the valley, but also the archeology of Central Asia.

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